

LONG TERM OUTCOMES IN PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH SECONDARY CHONDROSARCOMA

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Objective

Secondary chondrosarcoma (SChS), arising from pre-existing benign cartilaginous lesions such as osteochondromas, is a rare malignant tumour with limited evidence guiding optimal surgical management and prognostication. We aim to evaluate the clinical outcomes, prognostic factors, and surgical complication profile in patients with SChS, with a particular focus on the impact of resection margin status on relapse-free and overall survival.

Methods

Patients(pts) with a confirmed diagnosis of SChS were included in a retrospective analysis. Median relapse-free survival (mRFS) and median overall survival (mOS) were analysed using the Kaplan-Meier; log-rank test was used to assess potential prognostic factors; Clavien-Dindo scale - to classify surgical complications.

Results

The cohort included 31 pts, predominantly male (67.7%), with a median age of 35.7 years (range: 18.5–71.3). Predispositions included solitary osteochondroma (n=21, 67.7%), hereditary multiple osteochondromas (HMO; n=3, 9.7%), enchondroma (n=2, 6.5%), Ollier's disease (n=1, 3.2%); in 4 pts (12.9%) no specific predisposition was diagnosed. Tumours were located predominantly in the lower extremities (n=19, 61.3%), followed by the trunk (n=10, 32.3%) and upper extremities (n=2, 6.5%). Subtypes included: peripheral (n=27, 87.1%) and central (n=4, 12.9%). Grades were: G1 (n=27, 87.1%) and G2 (n=4, 12.9%). All pts underwent primary SChS resection with endoprosthesis implantation (n=7, 22.6%), hemipelvectomy (n=3, 9.7%). Resection margins were R0 (n=18, 58.1%), R1 (n=9, 29%), and R2(n=1, 3.2%). Surgical complications were recorded in 19 pts (61.3%), with Clavien-Dindo grade \geq IIIA in 8 pts (25.8%). mRFS was 10.2 months (95% CI: 110.2–NA), with 5-year RFS and OS rates of 76.7% and 92.2%, respectively. mRFS was 10.2 months (95% CI: 110.2–NA), with 3- and 5-year RFS rates of 86.1% and 76.7%, respectively. mOS was 110.2 months (95% CI: 97.1–NA), with a 5-year OS rate of 92.2%. Pts with R0 resection showed improved mRFS and mOS compared to those with R1 or R2 resections.

Conclusion

Resection with negative margins (R0) remains the most important determinant of improved RFS and OS in SChS pts. Despite a high incidence of surgical complications, long-term prognosis is favourable and local control achieved in most pts with SChS.